

Modelling the Roles of Institutional Libraries in the Accreditation Exercises in Federal Universities of South-South Nigeria

Hudron Kingdom KARI

Department of Library and Information Science,

Federal University Otuoke

karihk@fuotuoke.edu.ng

DOI: <https://10.5281/zenodo.11110525>

Abstract

The objective of this study was to provide a model that explains the role of the library in the accreditation of academic programmes and to ascertain the operational philosophy that will best ensure that libraries contribute to the success of accreditation exercises in Nigerian universities. The descriptive survey was used for the study. The sample size was made up of 454 librarians. The result of the study showed that libraries have a significant role in the success of accreditation of academic programmes in Nigerian universities. In particular, such roles were needed in three areas: library collection, academic content, and staffing. The researcher also found that the inclusion of library management in accreditation schedules could determine how libraries play their roles during accreditation exercises. Finally, this study examined the operational framework that will best assist libraries in playing their roles in the accreditation of academic programmes in universities.

Keywords: Accreditation exercise; academic programmes; libraries; public sphere; Universities.

Research Sponsored by TetFund IBR Intervention through Federal University Otuoke

Introduction

The purpose of university accreditation programmes is to guarantee adherence to minimal academic requirements and foster excellence in Nigerian universities (Durodolu, & Okiki, 2023). To make sure that university curricula satisfy the needs of the labour market, these exercises entail assessing a variety of factors, including information resources, people, and the

teaching environment (Bassey, & Agboola, 2021). The process of accreditation also highlights how vital well-equipped library resources and services are, as they play a critical role in program accreditation. Research indicates that the quality of resources, such as academic staff, library facilities, and money, as well as the suitability of accreditation exercise requirements, have a substantial influence on the accreditation process (Umeh & Oguejiofor, 2017). University accreditation reports offer valuable insights into the assessment models and self-assessment procedures employed to evaluate the standard of academic programs and administrative administration. Nigerian universities grapple with accreditation challenges each time the National Universities Commission (NUC) gives notice of accreditation of programmes in departments, institutes and centres.

Accreditation can be defined as granting official approval by a standard accrediting agency to an institution due to meeting set requirements. It could also mean the process by which the quality and standard of educational institutions are assessed. NUC is the statutory body responsible for accrediting programmes in Nigerian universities. As a result of this act, the NUC has a minimum standard/benchmark that programmes in Nigerian universities must meet (Dada *et al.*, 2017). Many Nigerian universities are faced with numerous challenges in going through accreditation seamlessly because of their inability to meet the minimum academic standard that includes evidence of learning materials like journal articles, books databases and other electronic resources. The accreditation of programmes in Nigerian universities pays attention to staffing, academic content, physical facilities, library, funding and graduate rating, respectively (Danladi 2020). Libraries are also required to have facilities and materials that are commensurate with the population of students as well as the number of programme offered. This is to ensure that the library facilities are adequate to aid effective teaching and learning based on the student population and the programme approved.

Based on the scoring criteria, libraries are rated based 12 points, physical facilities 25 points, staffing 32 points, academic content 23-point, funding 5 and employers' rating of graduates 3 points (Danladi, 2020). Therefore, it can be seen that institutional libraries have essential roles to play in ensuring the success or otherwise of accreditation exercises in Nigerian universities. Institutional libraries are directly linked to many of the other scoring criteria. For example, institutional libraries play essential roles in ensuring high-quality academic content offered by universities. This is done through the provision of relevant learning resources to students. Institutional libraries promote quality education in universities by collecting and disseminating practical information that aids learning Fabunmi, 2013; Griadhi *et al.*, 2018; Oakleaf, 2011).

Within this context, it can be said that institutional libraries are symbols of academic excellence. Institutional libraries are also linked to employers' ratings of university graduates. When students have access to relevant materials during their schooling days, they will be solidly trained to offer good services to their employers, who will provide a positive rating about them during accreditation. Library facilities significantly contribute to preparing undergraduates for the outside world (Xu & Du 2019). Additionally, a collaboration between institutional libraries and management could recruit competent hands that will be useful during accreditation exercises. Adeola (2014) notes that libraries have essential roles to play in the accreditation exercises of various programmes in universities in Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

Despite the potential usefulness of institutional libraries in assisting departments for successful accreditations, there appears to be a disconnect between management and libraries during accreditation exercises. Therefore, the goal of this study was to provide a model that explains the role of institutional libraries in the accreditation exercise in Federal universities in South-South Nigeria. An analysis of this nature is essential because it will guide how to creatively deploy institutional libraries in ensuring that universities successfully go through accreditation exercises. Such a study is necessary because it will provide empirical data that will serve as a guide on how to position Nigerian universities so that they will be compete with their counterparts around the world favourably.

Objective of the study

The objective of this study was to provide a model that explains the role of the library in the accreditation of academic programmes in Nigerian universities.

The researcher also sought to ascertain the operational philosophy that will best ensure that libraries contribute to the success of accreditation exercises.

Research Question

What is the appropriate model that explains the role of the library in the accreditation of academic programmes in Nigerian universities?

What is the operational philosophy that will best ensure that libraries contribute to the success of accreditation exercises?

Literature Review

Institutional libraries are located in learning institutions to serve the knowledge needs of the institution involved. In institutions of learning such as universities, libraries provide practical learning and teaching materials for students and teachers. Harland *et al.* (2017) say that libraries are critical stakeholders in the university community, hence have a responsibility to support activities that promote academic excellence. Harland *et al.* carried out a study to determine how the university Library Director can ensure its usefulness to the university community. The study was conducted in Australia, involving 12 library directors of public universities. Their result showed that libraries align their activities with the university's vision while constantly coming up with innovative ways to add value to libraries. However, Harland *et al.* (2017) were silent on the role of libraries in the accreditation of programmes in universities.

The study of Harland *et al.* implies that university libraries are crucial for attaining the objectives of university education. According to Auten *et al.*, (2020) Hollister and Schroeder (2015) university libraries assist students and scholars in learning about new ideas and understanding existing knowledge in their fields. Ali *et al.* (2021) say that university libraries offer electronic and printed materials that assist scholars and students in functioning as members of the university community. According to Ulla and Ulla (2010), university libraries are service-rendering establishments that must take steps to ensure that they live up to the expectations of their parent organization. University libraries also form a network among themselves to share mutually beneficial information. For example, Verma (2015) conducted a study and reported that academic libraries play essential roles in ensuring that educational institutions achieve academic excellence. If academic institutions fall short of greatness, libraries also share part of the blame.

In universities, lecturers must teach and publish articles in journals as a requirement for a promotion. This tradition makes libraries central to the publishing culture because journals constitute a significant source of information from where lecturers access and utilize literature. This assumption is supported by the study of Alcock and Rose (2016). They conducted a survey and reported that university lecturers have positive attitudes towards the library, indicating that university lecturers acknowledge the critical role of their library in their research efforts. Cooke *et al.*, (2011) Hrycaj and Russo, (2007) Mi, (2015) note that collaboration is needed between

libraries and university lecturers to harness the benefits of libraries effectively. Brown *et al.*, (2015) Creaser and Spezi, (2012) Delaney and Bates, (2015) conducted studies and showed that university librarians believe that they should play a critical role in academic activities, including teaching. The implication is that librarians regard themselves as vital players in promoting academic excellence. Adeola (2014) did a case study of Fountain University Osogbo to ascertain its contribution to the accreditation exercise in the school and found that the library is at the centre of accreditation in the school. Adetunla and Familusi (2017) conducted a study to determine the impact of accreditation on the growth of academic libraries. The researchers applied a descriptive survey involving a sample of 125 participants. The study showed that although libraries have a significant role in accrediting academic programmes, conditions like lack of funds and neglect of the library when there is no scheduled accreditation make it difficult for libraries to effectively function during accreditation exercises.

Folorunso and Urhiewhu (2016) conducted a study to examine the role of academic libraries during accreditation exercises in universities in Nigeria. The researchers collected secondary data from published journal articles, books and Internet sources. The researchers found that universities face challenges during accreditation exercises include: the shortage of staff, and funds, staffing deficiency in libraries, and insufficient learning materials. The study also, revealed that the accreditation process is ordinarily fraudulent due to the inability of universities to meet the requirement.

Agbetuyi *et al.* (2017) carried out a study to examine the role of academic libraries in the accreditation exercise of educational programmes. The researchers utilized a case study as a research approach. Their result showed that the university library examined has played a significant role in terms of collection and assisting students, eventually contributing to the accreditation of academic programmes in the university. According to Rodrigues and Mandrekar (2020), libraries assist students in developing long term skills that make them become better citizens. Rodrigues and Mandrekar add that libraries are essential components of a university that cannot be easily ignored. Afebende and Ebaje (2008) cautioned that even though libraries are crucial, their usefulness can only be harnessed if efficiently used. This means that if the libraries in universities are not efficiently deployed, they may not be able to assist Nigerian universities in improving their quality rating. The central point to note here is that libraries serve as symbols of academic excellence in universities; therefore, they are at the centre of the accreditation of academic programmes.

Libraries of the 21st century are regarded as institutions that should apply business models so that they will be able to serve the purpose for which they were established effectively. As part of the business model approach, shared value is suggested as an integral approach enabling libraries to play their roles effectively. Porter and Kramer (2006) suggested the shared value theory to explain the role of the library in their environments. Accordingly, the researchers define shared value as choices which organizations make for their benefit and their immediate environment. Porter and Kramer (2011) further add that shared value entails formulating and implementing policies and programmes that benefit a business entity. Although the shared value theory was initially designed to explain the functionality of business organizations, it has been found helpful as a guiding principle for libraries. Koizumi and Widdersheim (2016) say that libraries can offer beneficial insight into the shared value debate by highlighting the essential links they share with the people they serve. Owen (2016) conducted a study involving a case study of libraries in Wales. He found that developing and implementing the shared library management system is a practical approach for ensuring that libraries perform optimally. Pan (2021) notes that shared value can serve as a valuable parameter to guide the actions of library workers vis-à-vis the decisions they make and the collection they assemble in libraries.

Neisha and Kit (2011) did a study wherein they examined the value-based practices in libraries using primary and secondary data. The researchers found that a value-based approach is a valuable strategy that will enable libraries to deliver on their mandate to the communities that they serve. To be value-driven, libraries must engage in activities that significantly benefit their immediate environment. Vaidyanathan and Scott (2012) note that shared value theory offers an opportunity for creating an atmosphere of mutual benefit. Corporate Citizen Magazine (2011) opines that the shared value is helpful for non-profit organizations because it explains how such entities can effectively live up to their mission. Koizumi and Widdersheim (2016) note that even though shared value theory can be applied to explain the role of libraries, the public sphere model is most helpful in explaining the role of academic libraries.

Theoretical framework

This study found expression on the public sphere theory. The public sphere is defined as the connection between the library and the public (Widdersheim, 2015). It focuses on the relationship between libraries and the people they are supposed to serve. Koizumi and Widdersheim say that the public sphere model has three fundamental features.

These are commons principle, legitimation and governance. By definition, the commons principle hold that libraries serve to connect their users with the more extensive global network. According to Aabø *et al.*, (2010) Widdersheim, (2015) commons principle is an aspect of libraries require that library administrators support services that will bring citizens together regarding issues of mutual interest. Within the context of this study, it can be argued that university libraries need to support programmes and activities that will be of benefit to the university community. Accreditation exercise is one of the activities of value to the university community. It, therefore, means that libraries must promote activities that will aid accreditation.

Another dimension of the public sphere model that libraries should consider in the service to universities is legitimation (Evjen, 2015; Ingraham, 2015). In this type of dimension, users of a library develop and sustain support for a library based on the perceived performance of such a library. Again, under this dimension, a library attempts to galvanize and propel its community of users during challenging times. Within the context of this study, it can be said that libraries have a responsibility to support universities during accreditation so that it will enhance the legitimacy of such libraries.

The last element of the public sphere model is governance. According to Widdersheim and Koizumi (2016), governance requires libraries to support as well as respond positively to the need of their environment. It argues that library administrators are required to respond to the need of the domain. This requires that libraries have a mechanism that enables them to be aware of important issues within their environment and come up with ways of addressing them. Within the perspective of this study, university libraries need to understand the accreditation schedule of their universities and liaise with appropriate individuals to make the exercise successful. This model was found useful because it offers the framework for evaluating the role of libraries during accreditation of academic programmes. Based on the theoretical literature reviewed, the following model is proposed for the study:

Figure 1: Study model

Figure 1 highlights the study model and the contributing role of university libraries in the accreditation of academic programmes in universities. According to the proposed models, the independent variables are the five essential assessment items on NUC accreditation criteria, such as staffing, funding, academic content, physical facilities, library collections and graduate rating. The dependent variable is accreditation while inclusion of libraries in accreditation exercise was the intervening variable. Based on the model above, the researchers hypothesized:

H1: Academic libraries have roles to play in staffing, funding, academic content, physical facilities, library collection and employers' graduate rating to enhance the successful accreditation of academic programmes in universities.

H2: Inclusion of library staff in accreditation exercise will moderate the relationship between libraries roles and the success of accreditation in universities.

Methodology

Design of the study:

The design that was used in this study was descriptive survey research. It is the most suitable design when a researcher seeks to describe and explain a phenomenon (Ale, 2020; Ogbonne, 2019; Kwaghtser, 2019; Kari, 2020). Therefore, the goal of this study was to describe and

explain the role of university libraries in the accreditation exercises of academic programmes in Nigerian universities. Consequently, a descriptive survey was most applicable in achieving this goal.

Location/population

The study was conducted in South-South Federal universities, namely the University of Benin, Benin-City, University of Portharcourt, Federal University Otuoke, University of Uyo, Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun and Nigerian Maritime University Okerenkoko, Delta State, respectively. The population of this study was made up of 1052 librarians from the study area.

Study Participants

The population of this study was 1052 while the sample size was a total of 454 librarians the researcher conducted a priori power analysis using the G*power programme version 3.1 to arrive at the sample size. The researcher ticked the parameters as power ($1 - \beta$) at 0.95, effect size (f^2) 0.05 effect size f , and $\alpha = .05$. Additionally, the researcher checked the test family was set as F-Test, while the statistic family was set as multiple regression. The researcher used priori power analysis so as to increase the chances of accuracy in the sampling. According to Madukwe *et al* (2022) periori power analysis is needed to increase the chances of accuracy in sample size determination. The result of the priori power analysis revealed that a sample size of 454 was needed to determine a statistical significance at the 0.05 alpha level. Figure 2 reveals the output of the analysis.

Figure 2 Output for sample size determination

Sampling Technique

The respondent-driven (RDS) chain referrals sampling technique was applied to sample the participants in this study. RDS as a sampling technique requires that initial participants are identified and then requested to recommend other potential participants. In addition, the researcher identified initial participants who suggested other potential participants. The process of recommending and selecting participants lasted for one month. It should be noted that the decision to make use of RDS was to ensure that only the desired participants were sampled. Ahmad et al (2022) used the sampling technique and the outcome showed that it is a useful sampling procedure.

Instrument for Data Collection

The questionnaire was used as the instrument for data collection. The researcher utilized the questionnaire because of its ability to generate data in large volumes. Five-point Likert scale was the response format for the questionnaire. This ranges from strongly agree to disagree strongly. Three experts validated the questionnaire with attention to the clarity of the items, logicality, and appropriateness. The experts' comments were found helpful in preparing a final version of the questionnaire instrument. The researcher also conducted a pilot study involving 30 participants to determine the instrument's reliability, which yielded a Cronbach Alpha value of .87, indicating that the instrument was reliable.

Data Analysis

The researcher used simple percentages, mean and standard deviation among descriptive statistics, while multiple regression was used among inferential statistics. The results were presented in tables. The inferential statistics were tested at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Out of 454 copies of the questionnaire that were administered, 423 copies representing 93% were returned and found beneficial. The study results further showed that the sample was 61% male and 39% female. Regarding age, the mean age was 32 years. Also, the mean number of years that the participants have been working with the library was ten years. The implication is that the participants have worked with the university libraries long enough to understand issues related to the university's accreditation exercises for academic programmes.

Table 1: MANCOVA results on the roles of libraries in accreditation exercise with inclusion of libraries in accreditation as the intervening variable

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Funding	1.5	.43	Rejected
2	Staffing	3.2	.56	Accepted
3	Academic content	3.3	.43	Accepted
4	Physical facilities	2.1	.67	Rejected
5	Employers' rating of graduates	2.2	.89	Rejected
6	Library collections	3.9	.65	Accepted

The result of the study as presented in Table 1 revealed that three of the six items presented were accepted as the roles of libraries in the accreditation of academic programmes in universities in South-East Nigeria. However, the overall result achieved a statistical significance, $p=02$; Wilks' Lambda=.702. Based on this result, the first hypothesis was supported. The researcher also examined the moderating effect of the inclusion of library staff in the accreditation exercise and this revealed a significant moderating effect, ($p=.02$). Based on this result, the second hypothesis was also supported and the researcher concluded with 95% confidence that the inclusion of library staff in the accreditation exercise will significantly moderate the role they play in during accreditations.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation *analysis of the operational philosophy that should guide the contributions of libraries in the accreditation of academic programmes in universities*

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Remarks
1	Shared value	3.1	.56	Accepted
2	Public sphere	3.3	.35	Accepted
3	Integration of both	3.5	.33	Accepted

In Table 2, the researcher sought to determine the operational philosophy that should determine the role of the libraries in the accreditation exercises of academic programmes in Nigerian universities. The result of the study showed that all the items presented were accepted as the operational philosophy that should determine the role of the libraries in the accreditation exercises of academic programmes in Nigerian universities. However, an integration of both philosophies was favoured as it had the highest mean score.

Discussion of Findings

The objective of this study was to provide a model that explains the role of the library in the accreditation of academic programmes in Nigerian universities. The study specifically focused on the evaluation guidelines normally used by the National Universities Commission (NUC). These are staffing, funding, academic content, physical facilities, library collection and graduate rating. The researcher also examined the moderating effect of the inclusion of libraries in accreditation exercises. Finally, the researcher ascertained the operational philosophy that will best ensure that libraries contribute to the success of accreditation exercises.

The result of the study showed that libraries have a significant role in the success of accreditation academic programmes in Nigerian universities. In particular, such roles were needed in three areas, namely library collection, academic content, and staffing. This result has extended of Adeola (2014) Folorunso and Urhiewhu (2016) that have examined the role of libraries in the accreditation exercises of universities. While most of these studies have acknowledged that libraries are essential in the accreditation of academic programmes, little attention was paid to the assessment of items of the National Universities Commission. Including these items is important because accreditation of academic programmes is based on

assessment criteria which should also be considered when investigating the role of libraries in the accreditation of academic programmes. Therefore, this addition has offered more details empirical evidence regarding the role of libraries in accreditation academic programmes in universities.

The result of the study also showed that the inclusion of libraries in accreditation exercise can aid or limit libraries from playing their roles in supporting the accreditation of academic programmes in universities. This result has extended studies of Agbetuyi *et al.* (2017); Rodrigues and Mandrekar (2020) that have examined the challenges that libraries face vis-à-vis accreditation of academic programmes in universities without focusing on the facilitating conditions. This means that for libraries to be able to contribute to the accreditation exercise of academic universities, there is the need to pay close attention to issues of funding, training inclusion, and staffing. Where these areas are lacking, it will be difficult for libraries to be able to assist departments and centres that are facing accreditation effectively.

Finally, this study examined the operational philosophy that will best assist libraries in playing their roles in accreditation of academic programmes in universities. The result showed that although both shared value and public sphere models offer good explanations, integrating both approaches offers better potential. This aspect of the study has extended previous studies such as Owen, (2016); Pan, (2021); Neisha and Kit (2011) that have examined the most appropriate model for library administration. This study has highlighted the need to combine shared value and the public sphere rather than focus on only one operation framework. Accreditation is a laborious exercise, and if a school has most of its programmes discredited, it will also have a very negative impact on the university library because the number of patrons will also reduce. For example, if a school has all its programme denied accreditation, the university library may not have patrons. Therefore, the issue of accreditation is both of shared value and the public sphere.

Summary of Findings

1. Libraries have a significant role in the success of accreditation academic programmes in Nigerian universities.
2. Such roles were needed in three areas, namely library collection, academic content, and staffing.
3. There are facilitating conditions that can aid or limit libraries from playing their roles in supporting the accreditation of academic programmes in universities.

4. Enabling conditions include including libraries in the accreditation schedules.
5. Although both shared value and public sphere models offer good explanations, integrating both approaches offer better potential.

Conclusion

Based on the result of this study, the conclusion is that libraries are essential in the accreditation exercises of universities. Libraries have roles to play in library collection, staffing and academic content. Also, the study concludes that the inclusion of libraries during accreditation can determine how they assist during such exercises. The researcher also concludes that the accreditation of academic programmes is an issue with shared value and public sphere implications. Therefore, it requires an integrative approach to ensuring that libraries contribute to universities' accreditation schedules of academic programmes.

The result of this study has practical, theoretical and scholarly implications. Practically, the result of this study has offered fresh perspectives to library administration by highlighting the need to apply an integrative model that combines both shared value and public sphere approaches in ensuring that libraries contribute to the accreditation of academic programmes in universities. This study also has theoretical implications by adding a fresh perspective to the shared value and public spheres argument. This addition has suggested an integrative dimension that could be found helpful by researchers interested in theorizing library administration and management issues. Finally, this study has implications for scholarship by providing a model that explains the role of libraries in the accreditation of academic programmes in universities.

Recommendations

Based on the result of this study, the researcher makes three broad recommendations: First, it is suggested that university administration should look at facilitating conditions such as the inclusion of the library management team in the accreditation schedule to reduce the challenges associated with accreditation exercises in Nigerian universities. In the second place, it is suggested that library administrations adopt an integrative model in their management approach so that libraries will be able to play their supportive roles during the accreditation of academic programmes in universities. Finally, it is recommended that libraries should be made an integral component of accreditation exercises.

Acknowledgement

The author wishes to acknowledge the funding received from Tertiary Education Fund (TetFund) Abuja through the Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, Nigeria who were instrumental to the successful completion of this work.

References

- Aabø, S., Audunson, R. & Vårheim, A. (2010). How do public libraries function as meeting places?”, *Library & Information Science Research*, 32 (1),16-26.
- Adeola, B. (2014). Accreditation and the academic library's role in undergraduate programs: A case study of Fountain University, Osogbo. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19 (10), 45-48.
- Adetunla, G & Familusi, E (2017). The impact of accreditation on the growth of academic libraries in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 1591.
- Agbetuyi, P., Adegbilero-Iwari, I. & Subair, R. (2017). Role of academic libraries in accreditation of courses and teaching programs: a case of Afe Babalola University library, ado – Ekiti. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 3,(1),16-24.
- Agboola, B. & Bassey, A. O. (2021). Accreditation exercise requirements adequacy and quality of resources in South-south federal universities, Nigeria. *Integrity Journal of Education and Training*, 5(2), 28-38.
- Ahmad, J., Ugwuoke C. J, Talabi, F. Okeibunor N. B., Aiyesimoju, A. Adefemi, V. & Gever V. C. (2022). Impact of social media-based intervention in reducing youths’ propensity to engage in drug abuse in Nigeria. *Evaluation and Program Planning*, 94,102122.
- Alcock E & Rose K (2016). Find the gap: Evaluating library instruction reach using syllabi. *Journal of Information Literacy* 10(1): 86–98.
- Ale, V. (2021). A library-based model for explaining information exchange on Coronavirus disease in Nigeria. *Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 1-11.
- Ali, N., Shoaib, M., & Asad, & Hussain, I. (2021). Research is a scientific capital: the role of university libraries in higher education institutions. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 5116.
- Auten, B., Croxton, R., & Tingelstad, C. (2020). Extending our reach: integrating librarians and library resources into Canvas. *medical Reference Services Quarterly*, 39(2), 101-112. DOI: 10.1080/02763869.2020.1734395
- Bassey, A. O., & Agboola, B. M. (2021). Accreditation exercise requirements adequacy and quality of resources in South-south federal universities, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Training*, 5(2):28-38. doi: 10.31248/IJET2020.079
- Brown RA, Wolski M& Richardson J (2015) Developing new skills for research support librarians. *Australian Library Journal* 64(3): 224–234.

- Cooke, L., Norris, M., Busby, N., Page, T., Franklin, G., Gadd, E., & Young, H. (2011). Evaluating the impact of academic liaison librarians on their user community: A Review and case study. *New Review of Academic Librarianship*, 17(1), 5–30. doi:10.1080/13614533.2011.539096
- Creaser C & Spezi, V. (2012). Working together: Evolving value for academic libraries. a report commissioned by SAGE. Loughborough: Loughborough University.
- Dada, M. S., Yakub I W & Tukei M. (2017). Accreditation is a quality assurance in Nigerian universities: the challenges. *International Journal of Advanced. Research* 5, 500-508.
- Danlad, S (2020). Issues and concerns in the use of system-wide accreditation as the major quality control mechanism in Nigerian universities. *International Journal of Humanities Social Sciences and Education* 7, (1), 42-48.
- Delaney, G. & Bates, J. (2015) Envisioning the academic library: A reflection on roles, relevancy and relationships. *New Review of Academic Librarianship* 21(1): 30–51.
- Durodolu, O. O. & Okiki, O. C. (2023). Evaluation of the Processes and Procedures of University Accreditation: Putting the University Academic Ranking in Perspective. In O. Onyancha & A. Tella (Eds.), *Impact of Global University Ranking Systems on Developing Countries* (pp. 228-239). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-8266-7.ch012>
- Evjen, S. (2015). The image of an institution: politicians and the urban library project. *Library & Information Science Research*, 37 (1), 28-35.
- Fabunmi, B.A. (2013). An investigation into the awareness, occurrence and preparedness for disaster management in selected academic libraries in Tanzania, East Africa. *Journal of Library, Educational Media and Information Studies (JOLEMIS)*.5(1) 1-15.
- Folorunso, F J & Urhiewhu, L. (2016). Roles of academic libraries in university accreditation in nigerian: challenges and way forward. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 9 (2),17-22.
- Griadhi, M., Suarni, N K; Marhaeni, N & Sutajaya, M. (2018). The effect of library services quality towards achievement motivation and learning achievement of undiksha students on Bali-Indonesia. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 1822.
- Harland, F; Stewart, G; & Bruce, C. (2017). Ensuring the academic library's relevance to stakeholders: The role of the Library Director. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, S0099133317301246-. doi:10.1016/j.acalib.2017.06.009
- Hollister, C. V., & Schroeder, R. (2015). The impact of library support on education faculty research productivity: an exploratory study. *Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian*, 34(3), 97-115. DOI: 10.1080/01639269.2015.1062584
- Hrycaj, P. & Russo, M. (2007). Reflections on surveys of faculty attitudes toward collaboration with librarians. *Journal of Academic Librarianship* 33(6): 692–696.
- Ingraham, C. (2015). Libraries and their publics: Rhetorics of the public library”, *Rhetoric Review*, 34 (2) 147-163.

- Kari, K. (2021). Predictors of the utilization of digital library services among women patrons in Bayelsa State, Nigeria: The moderating role of marital status. *Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(1), 86-94.
- Khan, A., Bhatti, R., Khan, G. & Ismail, M. (2014). The role of academic libraries in facilitating undergraduate and postgraduate studies: A case study of the university of Peshawar, *Pakistan. Chinese Librarianship: an International Electronic Journal*, 38, 36-49.
- Koizumi, M. & Widdersheim, M.M. (2016). Surpassing the business model: a public sphere approach to public library management. *Library Review*, 65 (6/7), 404-419. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LR-11-2015-0111>
- Kwaghtser, P. A. (2019). Impact of the conflict between farmers and herdsmen on food production in the agro-ecological Zone-B of Benue State, Nigeria. *Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 56-64.
- Mi, M. (2015) Expanding librarian roles through a librarian initiated and facilitated faculty learning community. *Journal of Library Administration* 55(1): 24–40.
- Madukwe, C, Talabi, F. Sanusi, B., Okunade, J. Ogbonne, I. Ajaebili, N. & Gever, V. C (2022). Why Separatists' Communication Messages Succeed (or Fail): The Contributing Role of Socio-Economic Status on Adherence to IPOB Directives among Residents of South-East Nigeria. *Journal of Asian and African Studies*, <https://doi.org/10.1177%2F00219096221117078>
- Neisha, H. & Kit F. (2011). Value management in academic libraries: A case study. *The Journal of the Association of Professional Engineers of Trinidad and Tobago* 40 (1), 26-33.
- Oakleaf, M. (2011). Are they learning? Are we? Learning outcomes and the academic library. *The Library Quarterly: Information, Community, Policy*, 81(1), 61–82. doi:10.1086/657444
- Ogbonne, I. P. (2019). Cutting the head as cure for headache: Exploring the economic impact of Niger Delta militancy on host communities. *Ianna Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 76-84.
- Owen, G.W. (2016). Delivering a shared library management system for Wales. *Library Management*, 37 (6/7), 385-395. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LM-04-2016-0032>
- Pan, D. (2021). Shared Values: Catalysts for Inspiring and Implementing Change in Library Collections. Retrieved from <https://digital.lib.washington.edu/researchworks/bitstream/handle/1773/46943/Shared%20Values%20PPT%20-%20Denise%20Pan.pptx.txt?sequence=4>
- Porter, M.E. & Kramer, M.R. (2006). Strategy and society: the link between competitive advantage and corporate social responsibility”, *Harvard Business Review*, 84 (12) 78-92.
- Porter, M.E. & Kramer, M.R. (2011). Creating shared value. *Harvard Business Review*, 89 (1/2) 62-77.
- Rodrigues, C. & Mandrekar, B. (2020). Impact of academic library services on students success and performance. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 4246.

- Ulla Hakala & Ulla Nygrén (2010). Customer satisfaction and the strategic role of university libraries , *International Journal of Consumer Studies* 34(2), 204–211. doi:10.1111/j.1470-6431.2009.00834.x
- Umeh., U. F. & Oguejiofor, C. S. (2017). Impact of NUC accreditation exercise on library and information in business education programmes of universities. 2(2)
- Vaidyanathan, L. & Scott, M. (2012). Creating shared value in India: the future for inclusive growth. *Corporate Social Responsibility: Practice, Theory, and Challenges*, 37 (2), 108-113.
- Verma, M. K. (2015). Academic excellence in higher education through web-based library services. *Contemporary Social Scientist*, 7(2), 56-63.
- Widdersheim, M.M. (2015). Governance, legitimation, commons: a public sphere framework and research agenda for the public library sector”, *Libri*, 65(4), 237-245.
- Widdersheim, M.M. & Koizumi, M. (2016). Conceptual modelling of the public sphere in public libraries. *Journal of Documentation*, 72(3) 591-610,
- Xu, F., & Du, J T (2019). Examining differences and similarities between graduate and undergraduate students' user satisfaction with digital libraries. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 45(6), 102072–. doi:10.1016/j.acalib.2019.102072